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NUMERICAL STUDY ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES INFLUENCING BALLISTIC IMPACT BEHAVIOUR OF WOVEN FABRICS USING CONSTANT TOUGHNESS APPROACH.

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Factors influencing energy absorption of woven fabric and Need of study :

Factors influencing Energy Absorption:

- Toughness of yarn:
- Friction:
- Boundary conditions:

Need of Study.

- Till date parametric study on influence of material properties on ballistic performance was done by changing one material property and keeping others constant.
- This resulted in change in toughness of material.
- More realistic approach was needed to find out best combination of material properties for enhanced ballistic performance.
- Very few literature has been reported on interlayer Coefficient of friction (COF) effects on ballistic performance.

Material Properties:

Material	Mat 1	Mat 2	Mat 3
Longitudinal Modulus (GPa)	16.3	65.5	262
Failure Strain (%)	11	5.5	2.75
Failure Stress (GPa)	1.8	3.6	7.2
Toughness (GPa/vol)	99	99	99

	Kevlar KM2	Kevlar 29	Spectra 1000	Zylon AS	Twaron
Young's Modulus (Gpa)	84.62	70.5	171	180	110
σ_{max} (GPa)	3.9	3.6	3	5.8	3
$\epsilon_{failure}$ (%)	4.58	5.5	1.8	3.2	2.6
Density (kg/m3)	1440	1440	970	1540	1450

Study 1: Energy absorption analysis using constant toughness approach

Striking Velocity	Mat 1	Mat 2	Mat 3
	Percentage of Energy absorbed by fabric.		
175	99.94	65.38	43.1
200	99.75	37.6	31.93
250	49.3	21.14	10.88
300	27.75	14.12	7.84
350	14.83	7.84	6.18
400	11.16	7.84	5.42
600	3.3	2.97	2.64
700	3.11	2.83	2.55
800	2.97	2.97	2.48

Study 2: Comparative study on energy absorption of woven fabrics.

	Toughness (MPa/Vol)	BLV (m/s)	Failure time(μ s)
Kevlar km2	89	101	52.5
Kevlar 29	99	112	65
Spectra 1000	27	60	55
Zylon	92.8	90	47.5
Twaron	39	54	35

- Material with low modulus and high failure strain absorbs maximum energy (evident by constant toughness approach)

- Mat 1 with Low longitudinal modulus and High failure strain absorbs maximum energy.
- Percentage of Energy absorption for all three materials decreases with increasing striking velocities.

- Nature of % decrease in energy absorbed is negative exponential.
- Results reveal that only high toughness is not sufficient condition for high BLV, it should have low toughness and high failure strain value.

Study 3: Effect of Interlayer COF on Energy absorption of different woven fabrics

COF	Kevlar km2	Kevlar 29	Spectra 1000	Zylon	Twaron
	Residual Velocity				
0	257	254	300	265	307
0.1	250	242	295	256	304
0.2	248	235	296	250	306
0.3	244	230	302	250	306
0.4	235	230	303	246	306
0.5	239	228	304	249	305
0.6	244	231	305	249	305
0.7	249	231	305	248	305
0.8	250	233	305	250	306
0.9	250	236	306	250	306
0.99	250	236	306	251	306

Material	Kevlar km2	Kevlar 29	Spectra 1000	Zylon	Twaron
Threshold COF	0.4	0.5	0.1	0.4	0.1

Results and Conclusion

- Low longitudinal modulus and high failure strain is best combination for maximum energy absorption.
- Energy absorption of material decreases as projectile striking velocity decreases.
- All the woven fabrics shows increase in energy absorption with increase in COF up to certain value after that energy absorption decreases and remain constant.
- Materials with high value of toughness, we can afford to increase COF to increase energy absorption.